

Isodidymocarpin, A New Chalcone from *Didymocarpus pedicellata*

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A new chalcone, isodidymocarpin, has been isolated from the leaves of *Didymocarpus pedicellata*. From spectral and chemical evidences, its structure has been settled as 2', 4'-dihydroxy-3', 5', 6'-trimethoxy chalcone (2).

IN course of our studies on the genus *Didymocarpus* (Fam. Gesneriaceae)¹⁻³, we undertook further chemical and biological investigations on the plant *Didymocarpus pedicellata*, which elaborates a number of polymethoxylated chalcones, a flavanone and quino-chalcones⁴⁻⁷. Extraction of the leaves of *D. pedicellata* with benzene led to the isolation of a new flavanone⁸, didymocarpin (1). The present paper reports the structure-elucidation of a new chalcone, designated as isodidymocarpin, now isolated from the petrol extract of the same source. The hitherto unpublished⁹, detailed studies so far made on didymocarpin (1), is also incorporated in this communication.

Isodidymocarpin, $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$ (M^+ 330), m.p. 138-39°, gave a greenish blue colour with alc. $FeCl_3$ solution indicating its phenolic nature. The UV absorption spectrum of the compound and a negative Shinoda test restricted its assignment to chalcone class. Functional group analysis of the compound revealed the presence of 3- OCH_3 groups (three 3H-singlets at 3.87 δ , 3.93 δ and 4.17 δ), a chelated -OH group (3380 cm^{-1} and a 1H-singlet at 12.83 δ , disappearing on D_2O exchange) and a conjugated carbonyl function (1630 cm^{-1}). The presence of a monosubstituted benzene ring was revealed by the IR (750 cm^{-1}) and NMR spectra (5-ArH multiplet at 7.50 δ). The IR spectrum also disclosed the presence of a complex aromatic substitution pattern (1580, 1425, 1395, 1350, 1050, 950 cm^{-1}). The 60 MHz NMR spectrum of isodidymocarpin also disclosed the presence of α - and β - protons of the chalcone system^{8,9} at 7.90 δ as a singlet.

The mass spectrum of isodidymocarpin provided evidence regarding the substituents present in rings A and B. It showed, in addition to the molecular ion peak at m/e 330 (M^+), two diagnostic peaks⁹ at m/e 253 (M^+-77) and m/e 226 (M^+-104) corresponding to the loss of a phenyl and styrene fragments respectively

from the molecular ion (M^+), confirming the unsubstituted nature of the B-ring of this chalcone.

The structure of isodidymocarpin was finally settled as 2 by its formation from didymocarpin 1 with 30% aq. NaOH.

Since chalcones are generally converted to the corresponding flavanones by the action of acids, an attempt was made to convert isodidymocarpin (2) to didymocarpin (1) with conc. H_2SO_4 in ethanol. However, it did not yield the expected flavanone 1 but gave rise to an interesting compound, m.p. 190-191°. The latter analysed for $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$ (M^+ 330). The IR spectrum (ν_{max}^{KBr} , 3300, 1620, 1475, 1350, 1220, 1080, 910 and 700 cm^{-1}) coupled with the UV (λ_{max}^{OH} 292 nm and $\lambda_{max}^{0.1NNaOH}$ 269 nm) and NMR spectra in $CDCl_3$ [2H-(m, 2.90 δ , AB-part), 1H-(dd, 5.40 δ , X-part), one chelated phenolic-OH (s, 11.40 δ , disappears on D_2O exchange), 3H-(s, 4.20 δ , one- OCH_3), 5-ArH (s, 7.50 δ), 3H-(t, 1.40 δ , one- CH_3) and 2H-(q, 4.10 δ , CH_2)] suggests that isodidymocarpin (2) has been converted to a flavanone¹⁰ having 2-OH, 1- OCH_3 and 1- OC_2H_5 groups in ring A and an unsubstituted B-ring. Of the 2-OH groups, one is chelated (11.40 δ , D_2O exchange) which is most probably situated *ortho*¹¹ to the other hydroxyl group (5.10 δ , D_2O exchange). It appears that isodidymocarpin must have suffered demethylation¹²⁻¹⁴ followed by ethylation of the 7-OH group as shown in Scheme 1.

The 6'- OCH_3 group of 2 is selectively demethylated because it is sandwiched between two oxygen substituents (here the carbonyl oxygen on one side and a methoxyl on the other)^{13,14}. Similar is the case with 5'- OCH_3 also¹³.

It is very likely that ethylation has occurred at the highly acidic -OH group situated *para* to a $>C=O$

function to yield the flavanone 3. A plausible mechanism is suggested in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Further, attempts to convert 2 to 1 with aq. 30% HCl did not give the latter and instead afforded a different compound, $C_{16}H_{14}O_6$ (M^+ 302), m. p. 156-57°. The IR spectrum γ_{max}^{KBr} cm^{-1} , 3280, 1625, 1490, 1360, 1230, 1070, 1020, 910 and 700) coupled with the UV (λ_{max}^{EtOH} 297 nm; $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-0.1(N)NaOH}$ 309 nm) and NMR spectra in $CDCl_3$ [$2H$ -(m , 2.90 δ , AB-part), $1H$ -(dd , 5.00 δ , X-part), one chelated phenolic-OH (s , 10.70 δ , disappears on D_2O exchange), two phenolic -OH (s , 6.90 δ , disappear on D_2O exchange), $3H$ -(s , 3.90 δ , OCH_3) and $5-ArH$ -(s , 7.10 δ)] suggests that 2 has been converted to a flavanone having 3-OH and 1- OCH_3 groups in ring A and an unsubstituted B-ring. This is also in accord with its mass spectral data. Of the 3-OH groups, one is chelated (10.70 δ) and it is most probably situated *ortho*^{1,2} to another hydroxyl group (6.90 δ). On the basis of the above spectral data, it is quite likely that the structure of the converted product from isodidymocarpin may be written as 4.

It is interesting to note that the flavanone 4 like didymocarpin 1 undergoes bathochromic shift^{1,5} of 12 nm with 0.1 N NaOH, thereby suggesting the presence of a 7-OH group. It is also soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate^{1,6}. Thus, the structure proposed for the flavanone 4 appears to be reasonable. Syntheses of

didymocarpin (1) and isodidymocarpin (2) as well as their transformation products are now in progress.

Experimental

The plant *Didymocarpus pedicellata* grows in the subtropical western Himalayan regions, India and the leaves of this plant were collected^{1,7} during the month of February-March, 1976. Petrol ether used had b.p. 60-80°. M. Ps. were determined on a sulfuric acid bath in open capillary and were uncorrected. For column chromatography silica gel (BDH, 60-120 mesh) was used. The UV spectra were recorded with aldehyde-free ethanol in a Beckman spectrophotometer. The NMR spectra were determined with a Varian A-60 instrument in $CDCl_3$ with TMS as internal standard. The mass spectra were recorded in an AEI-MS9 mass spectrometer using a direct insertion probe and operating at 70 EV.

Extraction and chromatography of isodidymocarpin 2 :

Air dried powdered leaves of *Didymocarpus pedicellata* (1.5 kg) were exhaustively extracted (25 hrs) with petrol ether in a Soxhlet apparatus. The solvent was evaporated and the concentrated extract (75 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (350 g). The chromatogram was eluted with solvents of increasing polarity. Benzene eluates on evaporation gave a reddish solid (6.50 g) which was further purified by rechromatography over silica gel (150 g). Elution of the chromatogram with petrol ether-benzene (1 : 1) afforded an orange-red solid which on crystallisation from petrol ether furnished isodidymocarpin 2 as orange needles, m. p. 139-140°; TLC; R_f, 0.49 (benzene-ethylacetate, 9 : 1) and 0.60 (benzene-ethylacetate, 8 : 2). (Found; C, 65.34; H, 5.63; $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 65.45; H, 5.45). UV: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 328 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.6); $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-0.1(N)NaOH}$ 288 nm; $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-NaOAc}$ 328 nm; $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-NaOAc} + H_3BO_3$ 328 nm and $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-H_3BO_3}$ 328 nm; IR: γ_{max}^{KBr} 3380, 1630, 1580, 1425, 1395, 1350, 1050, 950 and 750 cm^{-1} ; NMR: (δ) 7.90 (s , $2H$, *trans*-olefinic), 12.83 (s , chelated phenolic-OH, disappeared on D_2O exchange), 3.87 (s , $3H$, OCH_3), 3.93 (s , $3H$, OCH_3), 4.17 (s , $3H$, OCH_3), 7.50 (m , $5-ArH$) and 5.30 (s , phenolic-OH, disappeared on D_2O exchange); MS: 330 (M^+ , base peak), 253, 226, 211 and 183.

Isomerisation of isodidymocarpin 2 to a flavanone 3 with sulfuric acid :

To isodidymocarpin 2 (400 mg) dissolved in ethanol (60 ml), 4.8 ml of conc. H_2SO_4 was added and the mixture was refluxed for 60 hrs on a water bath. The gummy residue obtained was suspended in water and repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed, dried and evaporated to give a gummy substance which was then purified by chromatography over silica gel. Elution of the chromatogram with benzene-ethylacetate (9:1) afforded a yellow solid which on crystallisation from petrol ether-benzene furnished yellowish plates, m. p. 190-191°, 3. UV: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 292 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.1); $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-NaOAc}$ 292 nm and $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-0.1(N)NaOH}$

269 nm; IR: γ_{max}^{KBr} 3300, 1620, 1475, 1350, 1220, 1080, 910 and 700 cm^{-1} ; NMR: (δ) 2.90 (m, 2H, AB-part), 5.40 (dd, 1H, X-part), 11.40 (s, chelated phenolic-OH, disappeared on D_2O exchange), 5.10 (s, phenolic-OH, disappeared on D_2O exchange), 4.20 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 7.50 (s, 5-ArH), 1.40 (t, 3H, $-CH_2-CH_3$); MS: 330 (M^+ , base peak), 301, 226, 197 and 169.

Isomerisation of isodidymocarpin 2 to a flavanone 4 with hydrochloric acid:

To isodidymocarpin 2 (200 mg) was added 20 ml of 30% hydrochloric acid and the mixture was refluxed for 30 hrs on a waterbath. The gummy residue obtained was suspended in water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed, dried and evaporated to give an oily substance which on chromatography over silica gel and elution with benzene-ethylacetate (9:1) afforded a yellow solid. The latter crystallised from pet. ether-benzene as yellowish needles, m.p. 156-157°, 4. UV: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 297 nm and $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-0.1N NaOH}$ 309 nm; IR: γ_{max}^{KBr} 3280, 1625, 1490, 1350, 1230, 1070, 1020, 910 and 700 cm^{-1} ; NMR: (δ) 2.90 (m, 2H, AB-part), 5.00 (dd, 1H, X-part), 10.70 (s, chelated phenolic-OH, disappeared on D_2O exchange), 3.90 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 7.10 (s, 5-ArH) and 6.90 (s, two phenolic -OH, disappeared on D_2O exchange); MS: 302 (M^+ , base peak), 198, 152, 124 and 104.

Extraction and chromatography of didymocarpin 1:

Finely powdered leaves of *D. pedicellata* (1.5 kg) after extraction with petrol ether were exhaustively extracted (30 hrs) with benzene in a Soxhlet apparatus. The solvent was evaporated and the concentrated extract (15 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (250 g) and eluted with solvents of increasing polarity. Benzene-ethylacetate (9:1) eluates on evaporation gave a yellowish residue (2.5 g) which was further purified by rechromatography over silica gel (50 g). Elution with benzene-ethylacetate (9:1) afforded a pale yellow crystalline solid which on crystallisation from petrol ether-benzene furnished didymocarpin 1 as pale yellow needles, m. p. 103-104°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} -12.8^\circ$ (C=0.7, $CHCl_3$); TLC:Rf, 0.18 (benzene-ethylacetate, 9:1) and 0.25 (benzene-ethylacetate, 8:2). (Found: C, 65.50; H, 5.54; $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires, C, 65.45; H, 5.45).

Isomerisation of didymocarpin 1 to isodidymocarpin 2:

Didymocarpin 1 (200 mg) was dissolved in 30% aq. sodium hydroxide solution (30 ml) and immediately acidified with hydrochloric acid. The reaction mixture was suspended in water and repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed, dried and evaporated to give a gummy residue which was then chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with benzene

afforded an orange solid which crystallised from petrol ether as orange needles, m.p. 138-139°. It was found to be identical with 2 in all respects (m.m.p., Co-TLC, IR, UV, NMR, MS).

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